

GENDER MOTIFS IN EFFIONG JOHNSON'S *INSTALL THE PRINCESS* AND IRENE SALAMI'S *SWEET REVENGE*

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Abstract

*The polemics of gender issues and the growing sensitivity people attach to gender have drawn many a scholar into gender discourse. Meanwhile, for decades, gender dialogues and debates have largely focused on female marginalization and abuse by patriarchy while almost neglecting the female empowerment portrayed in literary works including those written by men. Until recently, prominent African male writers such as Achebe and Soyinka were heavily attacked for depicting women in their confinement or subjugation. On the other hand, recent discourse on gender reveals that these writers have consistently been fair and balanced in their portrayal of the female gender in their works. Despite the recent discourse, significant scholarly attention has almost neglected the evolving gender motifs explored in Effiong Johnson's *Install The Princess* and Irene Salami's *Sweet Revenge*. Adopting *Womanism* and *Motherism* as theoretical framework, this research examines and compares the gender motifs in both plays. The research discovers that both plays are united in their depiction of gender subjugation and abuse, gender disparity in political representation, gender assertiveness, sisterhood and revolution and gender empowerment and identity. The paper concludes that to empower the female gender and effect possible gender equality, there must be a positive change in the existing socio-political structures of patriarchy in order to usher in an articulate and intelligent female voice, through whom a collective consciousness, sisterhood and organised revolution could be achieved among the female folk. Through such bonding, more changes could be effected in the status-quo, leading to an expansion of the phenomenal female space in both traditional and cosmopolitan societies.*

Keywords: Gender, Motif, Feminism, Motherism, Womanism, Sweet Revenge, Install The Princess

1 Introduction

There is no doubt that gender is both a sensitive and polemic issue in our present world. People become increasingly conscious of their language and behaviour in order not to sound offensive to the opposite gender. In her monograph on *Snail-Sense Feminism*, Akachi Ezeigbo affirms that gender “is an important analytical category in the discourse of issues relating to men and women in the world today” (1). The cry for gender equality, Ezeigbo further observes, “Sounds and resounds everywhere especially in Africa where gender imbalance appears to be entrenched in different areas of life” (1). Thus, Ezeigbo emphasises the growing sensitivity of gender consciousness in our present world and its relevance in discourses on men and women, which forms the basis of this research.

Gender is sometimes misconstrued as sex. However, gender is not sex, but both are related and fundamental terms within the larger domain of feminism. An apt understanding of the basic differences between both terms is relevant for the comprehension of the present discussion. Pia Pichler and Sian Preece see sex as “biologically designed while gender is culturally constructed” (92). This implies that whereas sex explains why some – by their biological composition – are male and female; gender, on the other hand, is a cultural configuration which assigns stereotypical roles on each sex. Thus, society prescribes roles for the male gender different from those prescribed for the females. For instance, in Irene Isoken’s *Sweet Revenge* (henceforth referred to as *Sweet*), women are merely permitted in passive or supportive politics but not in active governance, which is solely men’s role in Nigerian society. Thus, the women, during the military era, were allowed to plead with the wives of the military leaders, lead protest marches, one even got shot by the soldiers, in their effort to wrestle power from the military. However, in the democratic governance, men pushed the women out of the centre – a situation that compels Cheryl, Sota’s English wife, to bemoan:

*It seems your country is made up of only men;
women are nowhere in your national agenda.
They are at the margin, nowhere near the
centre. Good luck to you all (11).*

Similarly, in Effiong Johnson’s *Install the Princess* (henceforth labelled *Install*), women are also not allowed in the ‘elders’ forum. Observing the wide

gap in the polity and being desirous for the needed change, Obong, the village head of Ekondo village, announces that “From now in Ekondo, one woman must be appointed to the elders’ forum” (36). To the Elders, such a development is not only unprecedented, but must be seriously opposed. Hence, they frown: “Women elders’ forum?” (36).

For decades, gender dialogue and debates have largely focused on female marginalization and abuse by patriarchy while almost neglecting the female empowerment portrayed in literary works including those written by men. Until recently, prominent African male writers such as Achebe and Soyinka were heavily attacked for depicting women in their confinement or subjugation. On the other hand, recent discourse on gender reveals that these writers have been consistently fair and balanced in their portrayal of the female gender in their works.

Thus, the debate on gender as so acknowledged is divergent. Based on this premise, this paper adopts a convergent stance on gender and argues that the observable gender marginalisation and disparity in African literary discourse has interestingly paved way for the female gender assertiveness/revolution and empowerment in modern Nigerian plays such as Effiong Johnson’s *Install the Princess* and Irene Salami’s *Sweet Revenge*.

Motif is a recurrent element, event or idea in a literary work. Meyer Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham define it as “a conspicuous element, such as a type of event, device, reference or formula, which occurs frequently in works of literature” (205). Therefore, gender motifs as used in this research concern themselves with issues or aspects which reflect gender in both plays such as gender subjugation and abuse by patriarch, gender disparity in political representation, gender assertiveness, sisterhood and revolution, gender empowerment and identity. The purpose is to analyse and compare these motifs in both plays from a feminist perspective. Attention has also been paid in the analysis to the dramatic techniques deployed by the playwrights in the texts.

2 Gender in African Literature

Explaining the gender ascription in literature, Imoh Emenyi in *Intersection of Gendered Voices* argues that in both oral and written literature across the ages, men are not only presented as the voice of literary enterprise, they also control

the public sphere by defining and restricting women; assigning the female gender the attribute of subservience and acknowledging to the male the position of power. She further quotes Haste as saying, “What each society prescribes as the appropriate role for the sexes becomes ‘the cultural theory of gender’ and the female child, in particular, is expected to learn them from birth” (38). In line with Emenyi’s observation, a female child is expected to see herself as unequal to her male counterpart and so must from birth learn feminine domestic roles such as cooking, child-birth, house cleaning, etc, which portray her as weak, unintelligent, subservient and docile compared to the masculine, domineering roles expected of a male child. Besides, she is planted in domestic sphere as a wife and mother because she is believed to be lacking thinking skills needed in public affairs when compared to men (Emenyi 38).

It is germane at this point to note that in African literary discourse, gender, which is rooted in feminism, has assumed divergent and antagonistic views. Charles Nnolim has reacted to this by calling the feminist movement in African literature “A House Divided” (134). To Nnolim, the feminist house is divided into so many camps, resulting in the different shades and theories such as Womanism, Motherism, Gynandrisms, Nego-feminism, Stiwanism, Snail-Sense Feminism and the rest. It can, however, be argued that the various theories notably are the propounded avenues for ending female exploitation, which itself is culturally defined. The changes in nomenclature serve to suit different cultures and contexts. Besides, although there is unity in diversity among these varied theories in scholarship, the current trend, it must be pointed out, has contributed to the polemics of the discourse and if not re-ordered, will, in near future, endanger the homogeneity, longevity and goal of the movement which hinges on woman liberation.

Consequently, the female gender in African literature is believed to have been unfairly represented. Until recently, it was argued that the female gender has always been cruelly maligned and subjugated by patriarchy both in reality and in the literature produced by pioneer male writers. Thus, Achebe, Soyinka, Ekwensi, Clark, Ngugi, Amadi, Armah, and others, have come under heavy attack for depicting women who are often reduced to the domestic sphere. For instance, Chikwenye Ogunyemi in *Women and Nigerian Literature* describes Nigerian literature as “phallic, dominated by male writers and critics who deal

almost exclusively with male characters and male concerns, naturally aimed at a predominantly male audience...” (65). This no doubt captures the feminist angst against patriarchy that Nigerian literature is not only masculine, but also male-authored creative works depict women derogatively and marginally.

Leonard Onwuegbuche corroborates this view and posits that:

The male writers who are favoured by tradition, ignore the concerns of women in their literary output. Male writers had portrayed the female characters as docile and subservient individuals who are appendages to men, whether as brothers, husbands or fathers (“Women and Supremacy of Tradition...” 35-36).

Onwuegbuche’s remarks interrogate the androcentric reflection of gender in precolonial and colonial Africa to the point that the male writers appeared to overlook the female positive image. Flora Nwapa castigates Nigerian male writers who, she believes, “portrayed women negatively or in their subordination to men” unlike Peter Abraham and Ousmane Sembene (“Women and Creative Writing...” 526). This anger undoubtedly motivated Nwapa to write *Efuru* with the intent to redeem the supposedly bastardised image of the female gender.

Thus, in line with Ini Uko’s remarks on the overwhelming impacts of knowledge and awareness on the contemporary African woman, African female writers and their male sympathisers have, in addition to exploring other female subversive gender motifs, empowered the female gender in their writings. According to her, Tess Onwueme for instance, portrays strong, assertive and revolutionary women in her dramaturgy. For instance, Osun, in *Then She Said It*, unites the oppressed women and leads a successive revolution against the capitalist upper class and patriarchy.

Interestingly also, Effiong Johnson and Irene Salami have dramatically explored the gender motifs of assertiveness, revolution and empowerment as solutions to female subjugation and abuse in *Install the Princess* and *Sweet Revenge* respectively. These form the thrust of this research.

Aisosa, Salami's protagonist, a consultant Gynaecologist, is severely subjugated and abused in a failed marriage by Sota, her ungrateful and inhumane husband, who marries a second wife while abroad. Divorced, Aisosa (now a Senate President) seizes the opportunity to revenge on Sota, who, having lost his job, comes back to beg her for remarriage.

On the other hand, Effiong Johnson's Princess is installed as the Queen of Ekondo. With the death of Obong Nkenang Udo Idem Ekpenyong Ekondo - king of Ekondo - and his two sons, a vacuum has been created on the throne. Against the opposition of the elders, the people move to crown the Princess the Queen of Ekondo. Besides, Princess defies the long-held custom of the male gender wooing the female and proposes to Udobong Nkenta. "Will it be too much to ask you to propose to me?" (107). Such revolutionary gender motifs conspicuously awaken the modern gender consciousness in African (Nigerian) gender literary discourse.

3 Theoretical Framework

The analysis of the plays is anchored on Womanism and Motherism, gender theories within the larger framework of Feminism.

Feminism is a literary theory which seeks to highlight the different categories of inequality in the society, especially as they affect the women. Rebecca Usoro sees feminism as the avenue for the expression of the female voice "(Gendered violence..." 259). Thus, in line with Judith Bardwick who sees feminism as the "implicit rejection of the lifestyle created by strong coercive norms that define and restrict what women are and can do..." (5), feminism aims at dismantling patriarchal restrictions imposed on women, empowering women and bridging the wide gap between male and female genders.

As a theory of feminism, Womanism is first credited to Alice Walker. In her work, *In Search of our Mother's Gardens: Womanist Prose*, Walker contextualises Womanism within blackness and feminine excessiveness. To Walker, a womanist is

a black feminist or feminist of color. From the black folk expression of mother to female children and also a woman who loves other women, sexually and/or non-sexually. Appreciates and prefers women's culture. ...and sometimes

loves individual men, sexually and/or non-sexually. Committed to survival and wholeness of entire people, male and female. Womanism is to feminism as purple is to lavender” (xii).

In other words, Walker defines Womanism as a movement for women of colour who love who they are and are not afraid to fight for what they feel is right. It is a movement that fights against race and class-based oppression, working to preserve the legacy and cultural traditions of women of colour.

However, Walker’s Womanist theory is generally regarded as Western. In Africa, Womanism is different. Chikwenye Ogunyemi is the first African (Nigerian) critic to use the term to reflect its Afro-centric notion. In her article “Womanism: The Dynamics of the Contemporary Black Female Novel in English,” she states her belief that Womanism is really about equitably sharing power between the sexes and between people of different races. According to Ogunyemi,

Womanism is black centred; it is accommodationist. It believes in the freedom and independence of women like feminism; unlike radical feminism, it wants meaningful union between black women and black men and black children and will see to it that men begin to change from their sexist stand (63).

Thus, this viewpoint serves as an umbrella theory of African ancestry in women’s struggle to effectively assert their humanity in the face of male-centred attitude towards their self-fulfilment in life. The theory further advocates for complementarity between the genders.

African Womanism, explains Ezeigbo, is distinguished from Alice Walker’s and Hudson-Weem’s brands of “womanism” and “Africana – Womanism” respectively by its identification with what Ogunyemi calls the “four Cs – conciliation, collaboration, consensus and complementarity” (20). To this end, Ogunyemi’s brand is “steeped in African communalism – a working together in an atmosphere of peace and mutual respect between men, women and children.” This, therefore, aims at gender complementarity and emancipation.

The theory encapsulates the stumbling blocks faced by women in Africa's patriarchal society. Ogunyemi writes "I have added husbands because they oppress women most" (*Africa Wo/man Palava...* 119).

Thus, it is realised that Womanism as theorised by Ogunyemi is rooted in Africanness, aiming at achieving a balanced representation of African women in literature.

Significantly also, African Womanism or Black Womanism touches on the woman's self-assertion, and sisterhood. To this end, Modupe Kolawole defines "Womanism" as "the totality of feminine self-expression, self-retrieval and self-assertion in positive ways" (24). She further posits that "womanism manifests and enhances African women's collective grouping and positive bonding as opposed to ideological bondage" (27).

On the other hand, Motherism, as advanced by Catherine Acholonu in her book, *Motherism the Afrocentric Alternative to Feminism*, serves to "empower African women as mothers" (Akachi Ezeigbo 22). Motherism, Ezeigbo notes, counters the ideas of feminism and works within the "popular gender roles and expectations that circulate in Nigeria's patriarchal society" (22). From the above explications of motherism, it is noticed that it focuses on the African woman as realising her essence and sense of fulfilment in motherhood.

Thus, Womanism and Motherism were selected because of their focus on the plights of African women, recognition of patriarchy as constituting some roadblocks to women's freedom, emphasis on gender complimentary, assertiveness, sisterhood, empowerment and to an extent, female identity. Thus, although Motherism might be interested in women only in African rural communities, Womanism is all-inclusive. The above themes constitute the gender motifs dramatised in the chosen plays and analysed in the subsequent section.

4 Analysis of Gender Motifs in the Plays

The analysis is presented simultaneously in both plays under the four themes below.

4.1 Gender Subjugation and Abuse

Patriarchal dominance, which manifests in various forms such as the subjugation and abuse of the female gender, exists in all cultures of the world,

including the religious worlds. In the worlds of Islam, Judaism and Christianity, the female gender remains a victim of oppression. In the Judeo-Christian world, for instance, the creation story tends to favour the male gender. The fact that God created Adam first before He created Eve from the rib of Adam (Genesis 2: 21-23) has been reinterpreted by many a feminist to have given impetus to patriarchal subordination of the female gender in all spheres of human relations in Africa and in other climes. Ini Uko in *The Feminine Ontology...* affirms this notion and observes that the belief has made it “easy for men to control women socially, politically, sexually, economically, etc.” (35); hence, the need for a desired change of the gender matrix in the contemporary society, which will pave way for the female gender empowerment and gender balance.

Thus, Effiong Johnson adroitly demonstrates his profound awareness of his Ibibio traditional values in *Install*. In it, he dramatises a typical African society that is steeped in patriarchal dominance with a high level of female suppression. Still, the playwright presents Ekondo land in crucial and urgent need of a positive change. With the sudden exit of Obong Nkenang Udo Idem Ekpenyong Ekondo, King of Ekondo; the tragic death of his two elderly sons – Ubokudom and Uko – in a plane crash while on a flight back from America for the obsequies of their royal father; the disability of his surviving son, Etiowo, a vacuum has been created on the royal throne, which must be filled in line with the dictates of tradition. The only capable child to occupy the empty seat is a woman, Princess, whose chances are not favoured by tradition. It is a taboo for a woman to rule Ekondo! Hence, the land is thrown into an imbroglio. Ukarakpa – the oldest member of the royal executive council of Ekondo – announces to the council:

The matter before us needs everyone’s intuition to be at alert. We shall be grappling with an issue which dimension, our fathers never had to deal with in their time...the very esteemed last king of Ekondo, has to be succeeded by his child, in keeping with the traditions of Ekondo. Who should succeed him? (60-61).

The conflict of the play hangs on this question. In their struggle to resolve this unprecedented conflict in the land, Ekondo elders reveal their patrifocal conservatism, in the face of emerging cultural dilemma and modernity.

First, Ekondo land, like Umuofia in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, places high premium on manliness with no regard for women. Men are traditionally empowered to rule, control the people, make progress in the land and be praised for their exploits, while the women are restricted to the home as care givers and tactically excluded from governance. The royal council is a composition of men as elders, whose allegorical names connote suppression, exploitation, strength, and manliness – Ukarakpa (a boa), Ukpotio (strength) and Nkakat (termite). Their highly metaphorical dialogues further affirm this stand.

Ukarakpa: The *he-goat* cannot hide its presence well, except blocked nostrils are members of the search party. The brown *chameleon* on the bark of the tree, yesterday, is the green one on the leaf, today...

Ukpotio: Ukarakpa...The *wise head* of Ekondo...Ekondo is blessed with *men* like you. *Men of commitment* for the *progress* of their *father land*. That even with a new *wife at home*, you could disentangle yourself to be here before the rest of us, proves your unmatched commitment to the affairs of Ekondo.

Nkakat: Did you say “unmatched commitment”? The old cargo wanted to save his *breadth* from the young *woman*. He readily found excuses from her to be here with the king, rather than gasp for breadth with his failing *stamina before the young woman*.

Ukarakpa: I don't blame you...I've told you show me half of the cost of the *dowry*, and I shall balance the rest for you; so that you could test your *stamina* with a fresh blood. *Nne Nkoyo is old and weak...* (19) (emphasis mine).

... (On his feet) My *bed* is an *attractive place* to retire to. *Nne Nkoyo must be missing me already...* (56) (emphasis mine).

From the excerpt, we notice the use of such androcentric animal symbols as the “he-goat,” and the “chameleon.” They symbolise and emphasis manliness in the society. Also “men” are eulogised as “wise” and those who are “committed” to the “affairs” and “progress” of their “father land” and not mother land (recall Nigeria's national anthem). Thus, they are linked with

progress and commitment. Again, men (even the aged ones) test their “stamina” with fresh women, suggesting oppression or conquest of the female gender.

On the other hand, the female gender is on the receiving end. As servants imprisoned at “home”, perhaps as a consequence of the “dowry” with which men “purchase” them from their parents, the women are depicted as care givers and sports on the “bed” to be enjoyed by men. Besides, they are stereotyped as “old” and “weak” like Nkoyo, to be discarded by the men at will and then the young women with fresh blood are brought in to replace them. Therefore, the men practise polygamy and betrayal. The imagery of Ukarakpa disentangling himself from his woman portrays women as cogs in the wheels of progress which must be overpowered, subdued as a boa would do its prey and then either swallowed up or thrown out of the progressive path of men. In that sense, the female gender is associated with retrogression and stones of stumbling destined to be conquered.

Furthermore, in marriage, women are reduced to the status of slaves by their men, in consonance with Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie’s argument that “it is within marriage that the Nigerian woman suffers the most oppression...” (75). Irene Salami, on her part, obviously indicts the men on this aspect of gender subjugation. Thus, female subjugation and abuse is a predominant gender motif portrayed in Salami’s *Sweet*. Dr Aisosa Ojo – the home-based wife of a chauvinistic, self-centred husband, Dr Sota – remains faithful to the mother Africa symbolism: Great mother of four children, supportive, loyal and respectful. Yet, she is a victim of suppression in marriage. In the first instance, she has suffered deceit, abuse, betrayal and neglect from her husband, who, for eight years, has abandoned her to take care of their four children and three others in Nigeria, while in his luxurious sojourn in London. With the support and consent of pregnant Aisosa, Sota leaves Nigeria for London for his Ph.D in International Relations which was originally to last for four years. But Sota marries another wife, a British by name Cheryl, unknown to Aisosa, and so decides to fabricate lies to justify his prolonged stay in London. Sota confesses to his deceit at the very opening of the play:

I remember telling my wife Aisosa when I left, ‘You stay back to take care of our children while I go in search of the Golden Fleece.’ Like a dutiful wife, she obeyed. She has

faithfully waited for my return all these years. I have fabricated tales after tales each day to explain my prolonged stay in England. I have taken up a job and settled comfortably in London (1).

Abandoned by her husband for eight years, Aisosa is compelled by poverty and the challenging domesticity to develop many hands for the many mouths in the home. With the meagre N10,000 monthly allowances instead of N40,000 promised her by her husband, Aisosa struggles singlehandedly to cater for the large family. In the process, she loses the spark and the youthful femininity that was once her luring bait for Sota. In consequence, she is severely abused, on his return, by her husband who stigmatises and labels her as “dull and drab” as portrayed in the following dialogue:

Sota: Sosa, I must be frank with you, you no longer excite me. You are too dull and drab. The spark that used to be in your life is no longer there.

In reaction, Aisosa laments her plights:

Aisosa: No doubt, it’s gone. What did you expect? Abandoned by a husband, no job, on a meagre allowance of N10.000 a month, lost my dear parents who were so supportive, struggling to build a house for you and saddled with four children, did you expect to return home to meet a model? If you did, wouldn’t you have been surprised?

Sota: That is no excuse for your becoming so drab. When I married you, you were so full of life, so much fun to be with. What has happened to you, Aisosa? Tell me, what happened to that Aisosa?

Aisosa: Sota you murdered her. Of course, I was full of life; I was young, married to a visible person. My children had a father, your mother had a son, but for the past eight years... I have been a father, mother, doctor, driver, tailor, nurse, extra lesson teacher, researcher, daughter in-law and all others (26).

This has x-rayed the dimensions of her masculinist torture, abuse and subjugation in marriage. It affirms the stand of Helen Chukwuma that the “female subjugation is never so apparent as in marriage” which reveals “the

plight and misfortunes of many women despised, relegated and exchanged who were abandoned like a worn-out or out-dated *boubou*” (*Accents in the African Novel*, 31).

Besides, gender subjugation and abuse thrives severest in wifhood and motherhood. It is in both marriage institution and motherhood that gender denigration is most found to rear its ugly head. Since wifhood and motherhood can only express themselves in womanhood, Aisosa is a typical African wife, mother and, of course, a woman. When asked by Sota (“Mr Beento”) “why can’t you wear trousers?” She shouts back at him, asserting her womanhood “What do you take me for? I am a WOMAN and not a girl Sota” (emphasis mine) (25).

Thus, as a wife and mother, Aisosa is made a kitchen or home material, a care giver and a dependent other, similar to Aisha Buhari who, her husband (President Buhari) openly says, belongs to “my kitchen, my room and the other room.” Dr Aisosa, is asked by her husband to resign her job as a consultant Gynaecologist only to remain at home as a full time house wife and a caring mother to his children. She tells Ede, her friend: “He wanted me to be home for him and the children” (34). Ede frowns at Sota’s attitude and sees it as “selfish expecting you to be drowned in domesticity and motherhood and yet remain a model” (34).

After the Senatorial elections and emergence of Sota as a Senator in the new Democratic dispensation of Nigeria, Sota plans to divorce Aisosa. Nosa, Sota’s friend, confronts him and reminds him of her sacrifices as a caring mother and loving wife for him.

Nosa: ...Sota, remember, this woman was a consultant gynaecologist when you asked her to resign her job and stay home to care for your children. She would have become the chief Medical Director of that hospital by now, considering the fast pace of her upward mobility. That is very, very cruel. Sota. You better reconsider your stand (21).

Like many chauvinistic husbands such as: Ada’s Francis in Buchi Emecheta’s *Second Class Citizen*, Ramatuolaye’s Modou Fall and Aissatou’s Modou Ba in Mariama Ba’s *So long a Letter*, Sota is indeed cruel, high handed and non-

appreciative of his sacrificial wife and mother of his children. Hence, Nosa goes further to ask him to “show appreciation for our wives,” (Aisosa and Ede), whose mobilisation and high regard drew the women out to vote for him with the hope of an improved condition for the subjugated wife and mother.

Nosa: Our people have deep respect for Aisosa. They admire the way she comported herself in your absence. Some other women would have abandoned their responsibility and ran off with another man. She has been a good wife and mother, to you and your children, made a lot of sacrifices and the women wanted to reward, encourage and honour her by coming out to vote for you hoping her lot will improve from now on (18).

Furthermore, an abuse in the form of betrayal or marital unfaithfulness is about the cruellest maltreatment a wife would hate to suffer from her husband. Sota’s second marriage to a white lady, Cheryl, while in London, is a devastating blow to Aisosa, who knew nothing of the betrayal even after Sota’s return and election. After her divorce, Aisosa leaves Benin with her four children and goes to lodge with Ede, her friend and confidant in Abuja. By this time, Sota had brought Cheryl and their new baby to his government house in Abuja. A day came when Ede let out the news:

Well, Aisosa, Sota is married to a white woman. He married her while in Britain and she is living with him here in Abuja (36).

Then Aisosa exclaims:

Oh my God, was that why he was looking for excuses to discard me? Ah, wonders will never cease. I wish him well. The woman is probably not aware that he is still legally married (36).

Despite this seeming passivity and wishful disposition assumed by Aisosa in her abusive circumstance, one can imagine the degree of bitterness and regret in her mind from that moment. Salami, through this motif, skilfully explores the destabilising and reductive influence of polygamy in modern times. No doubt, she lampoons this selfish practice through her character, Nosa, who questions Sota on his scheme: “Look around your peers, how many people do

you see marrying more than one wife? Polygamy is fast disappearing. It is no longer an option amongst our people here” (21).

The ugly experience is reminiscent of Ramatoulaye’s betrayal by her late husband, Modou Fall, who, while alive, married a new wife, Binetou. Indeed, Ramatoulaye’s bitterness is clearly captured in her introspection thus:

Was it madness, weakness, irresistible love? What inner confusion led Modou Fall to marry Binetou?... And to think that I loved this man passionately, to think that I gave him thirty years of my life, to think that twelve times over I carried his child...In loving someone else, he burned his past, both morally and materially. He dared to commit such an act of disavowal. And yet, what didn't he do to make me his wife! (So long a letter, 11-12).

Similarly, in loving someone else, Sota has burned his first covenanted love with reckless abandon. He seems to have allowed machismo, ego, passion and selfishness to becloud his sense of reasoning. Investigating gender inequality in South eastern Nigeria, Daniel Jordan Smith posits:

In a time when global notions about gender equality circulate widely in Nigerian vernacular forms, and in a society where men (and to some extent women) still enforce a system of gender inequality that allows men much more autonomy after marriage including a powerful double standard about infidelity – these issues have become the subject of significant personal and social preoccupation (5).

From Smith’s observation, it is a reality that men (husbands) are generally allowed much more freedom by tradition to cheat and betray their wives while in marriage and this trend highlights the complexity and contradictions of Nigeria’s (indeed Africa’s) disturbing gender dynamics.

Then of all forms of gender subjugation and abuse, the worst was yet to come. It finally came with Aisosa’s divorce from marriage and disgraceful eviction from the very house she built with her late father’s wealth as at the time Sota

was cruising with another woman in London. The dialogue below captures the sad moment:

Sota: Enough of that, I am sick and tired of you, Aisosa. For your information I am filing for a divorce.

Aisosa: Well, I expected it earlier than now. I saw it coming; I am not surprised at all. In any case, what have I done to warrant a divorce?

Sota: Everything in the book. I have just listed some of them.

Aisosa: Don't you think we should give ourselves sometime to renew our relationship for the sake of the children? Sota please be patient and don't be too hasty. Don't be selfish. The children need a father; they have never really had one.

Sota: No, I have had enough. You can keep the children; find them another father if you wish. Please stay out of my path.

Aisosa: So your mind is made up then?

Sota: Yes, it is. No going back. I want to move on with my life.

That day, Aisosa tearfully bows out of her marital home in shame, empty. She weeps for three months. In her lament to Ede, who later accommodates her in Abuja, she explains:

You know what, Ede? I was not really weeping for Sota, after all he has never really been there for us. I wept for losing all I ever worked for, all I ever possessed, I wept for my house; it reminded me of my parents. I wept because I felt society will reject me and see me as a failure. As you know, in our society, a woman bears all the blame when a family breaks up (35).

Truly, African society often castigates the woman whenever there is separation. She is often judged guilty for packing her things out of her husband's house without seeing any fault from the husband. She will from that

time be rejected and humiliated in the society as a failure and irresponsible. And this has evidently illustrated the explication of *gender* as a socio-cultural construct. However, when will our society begin to blame the man for undue subjugation of his wife, betrayal, battering, forceful eviction, denigration and abuse of humanity? When?

Sota, himself an absentee husband and father, rejects Aisosa because of his new found love, Cheryl, who equally suffers similar fate and later walks out of wedlock too, with the discovery of Sota's intrigues and betrayal (his previous marriage with Aisosa, unknown to her until her landing and brief stay in Abuja). Thus, both women undeservedly suffer abuse from a man they call their husband for the mere fact that they are women, wives and mothers.

4.2 Gender Disparity in Political Representation

Nigerian (indeed African) women, as observed by Akachi Ezeigbo, are "disadvantaged in politics" (*Snail Sense Feminism...8*). Most significant positions are occupied by men. Occasioned by obnoxious traditional(patriarchal) laws and gendered stereotypes, the women are marginalised and discriminated against; intentionally schemed out of active and meaningful political participation and are merely allowed to take part in passive and non –influential positions. It is in this light that Adrienne Rich, cited by Grace Okereke, defines patriarchy as:

...the power of the fathers: a familial-social, dialogical, political tradition, law, and language, customs, etiquette, education, and the division of labor, determine what part women shall or shall not play, and in which the female is everywhere subsumed under the male ("African Gender Dialogics..." 261).

This gender motif conspicuously runs through the plays.

In *Install*, the playwright portrays and condemns the suppressive manners through which the male gender capitalises on the patriarchal machinery to dislodge the female gender from political representation. The first is the legal system. The executive council of Ekondo land is made up of "wise" and "aged" men of 70 years old, regarded as the "elders" and "custodians of the traditions of Ekondo" (71). Together with the king (strictly a

male), the cabinet legislate and govern the people of Ekondo.

Thus, with the exit of Obong Ekondo (the king), the vacuum created can only be filled by the king's son. Meanwhile, soon after the funeral of the king, Ufok iban was chosen by the women folk as their representative at the council. This new development came as a result of the amendment of the law and recommendation by the late King prior to his death. Then at once, we notice the disparity and imbalance in the gender equation among the elders – 1: 3.

With the introduction of the wise and articulate female voice, the executive debate assumes a dramatically new dimension. Consequently, on the succession debate, Ufok iban boldly moves a motion that:

...one of the king's children with superlative ability is still remaining. The throne of Ekondo fits the Princess (61)

The three male elders expectedly are taken aback and so they echo in uniformity “The Princess?” shaking their heads in bitter disagreement. In response, Ukpoto retorts:

That was well-reasoned. Well-spoken, Ufok iban. You are very correct, except that you did not remember that the *throne of Ekondo is exclusively for kings and not queens*. All through the years, as far as we can remember, there was no time in the life of Ekondo that a woman ever ruled. This precedence must be continuously maintained (62) (emphasis mine).

Patriarchy will always insist on the maintenance of the status quo. Even when the debate becomes hotter and Etiowo (the disabled son of the late King) comes out to relinquish his position to his sister, Ukarakpa still insists: “The throne of Ekondo cannot be occupied by a woman” (75).

Unable to resolve the conflict, the elderly men decide to consult the young men for their opinion on the matter, but neglect the young woman. This is another scheme by patriarchy to disparage between the two genders and deny the

female folk the opportunity to take part in decision making process. So, in reaction, at the next council meeting, the village women bond themselves in protest and invade the council. Nne Mmatim – the oldest woman – leads the protest:

We heard about your meeting yesterday. We also heard that you sought help from the young men. But you neglected the young women as if they were nobodies. That's why we came. As you can see, we are representing all the families of Ekondo; because we have a stake in the affairs of Ekondo (77).

This action of the women is unprecedented, but it is very clear from this point that the women are beginning to have a voice in the affairs of Ekondo, having regained their collective consciousness of their marginalisation and oppression by the Marxist patriarchy. Hence, one should expect that a full-blown rebellion by the exploited women is imminent.

We also notice the third strategy of patriarchal control and subordination of the female gender which clearly reflects gender disparity and supremacy in politics. It is the tactical deployment or manipulation of the male-cults: instruments of intimidation and suppression. Thus, at the rebellious chanting of “INSTALL THE PRINCESS!” by the rebellious women and girls of Ekondo, the male elders are automatically brought into confusion. In order to frighten the female folk from the council, two machet-flaring Ekpo masquerades storm the scene, following the rattle and invocation by the cult leader. Their strategy seems to yield positive results as the “girls are scared and confused...are cordoned off” by the daring elderly women” (79). But the men have forgotten that the women have their weapons of intimidation too, more dreaded than the male-cults!

The case is not different in Irene Salami's *Sweet*. The women are discriminated against in mainstream politics. Nigeria has just come out from military government and Dr Sota is being invited by his people to return from London for a Senatorial election as their candidate. Meanwhile, the women, during the military regime, sacrificed their lives in the deadly fight for the liberation of the country from the shackles of “militocracy” (6). Regie (Sota's friend in London)

explains to Cheryl the role of the women:

*Oh! Our dear mothers, they put in all they could.
They held rallies, pleaded with the wives of military
leaders, led protests marches; in fact, one woman
who strongly opposed them was shot dead one early
morning. She paid dearly with her life (9).*

Unlike the women, the men, according to Regie, were “hiding in their closets. When they dared to come out they wore badges, badges that identified them with the military government” (10).

However, one is sad to observe in the play and in reality that the active role of the women before now has been forced into passivity by the men who have taken over the democratic governance. And so when Cheryl asks “What role will the women play in this new Nigeria?” Sota responds:

*Relax don't be too hasty Cheryl. We have just
commenced. All will be worked out later. As soon as
things are sorted out, they will be duly compensated
(10).*

Cheryl: Did I hear you say “compensated”?

Sota: Yes, what about that?

Cheryl: You talk as if they are not part of the system. They should be involved right from the start.

Sota: Well things don't work that way in Africa. We take a lot of things into consideration.

Obviously, in Africa, as noticed from the above gendered debate, the female gender by virtue of her femininity, is not considered good enough for any influentially significant position in governance, unlike in other climes where women such as Angela Merkel of Germany, Hillary Clinton of the US, Yuri Fuykawa of Japan, Luciana Leon of Peru, Alina Kabaeva of Russia, etc, have been allowed to play lead roles in national and world politics. On the contrary, it appears African countries are made up of only men, as women are

discriminately shut out from the national agenda as spitefully observed by Cheryl:

It seems your country is made up of only men; women are nowhere in your national agenda. They are at the margin, nowhere near the centre... (11).

Furthermore, Cheryl – a woman right activist – understands gender exclusion and marginalisation as inhumanity: “You can imagine what it is like to be excluded from a system that belongs to all. Being marginalised is dehumanising” (13). Moreover, where women are politically “compensated” in governance, the ratio between the genders will be absurd. In other words, when Cheryl probes to learn from Sota, who returns from a nocturnal Senate meeting, how the female Senators cope with the rigours of Nigerian politics, he retorts:

Just two of them, they have no choice. If they want to remain, they have to abide by the rule (37) (emphasis ours).

As reflected, only *two* out of a hundred and more Senators are women, who must abide by the stringent, unfair rules made by men, “if they want to remain” in politics. The case is not different from the Senegalese National Assembly. Recall Ramatoulaye’s indictment of their Assembly with the label, “That male Assembly” (*So Long...60*). She loudly questions the ridiculous female-male ratio upheld by Daouda Dieng and his male Assembly:

Four women Daouda. Four out of a hundred deputies. What a ridiculous ratio! Not even one for each province (60).

It should be stressed that, in Nigerian situation, this negligible number of the women representatives no doubt symbolises the only 7 female Senators (out of 109) in the current 8th National Assembly. For the House of Representatives, 15 female lawmakers currently represent their federal constituencies. It is therefore not surprising why it is difficult for the 22 female lawmakers as against their 338 male counterparts are unable to vote their “Gender and Equal Opportunities Bill” into law since 2011. To correct this imbalance and in line with the vision of the playwright, Regie charges Sota, who has been chosen to represent his people, to “champion the fight against the attitude of shutting

women out”. According to him:

As a nation we must constantly be conscious of the fact that Nigeria is made up of men and women. Mainstreaming women into governance is a task we must all carry out at all cost (11).

By this advocacy, gender equality in governance and in other institutions can only be achieved through aggressive gender assertiveness, sisterhood and revolution as further explored in the plays.

4.3 Gender Assertiveness, Sisterhood and Revolution

People’s consciousness that the subjugation, marginalisation and deprivation they suffer can be altered compels them to seek possible ways of effecting the desired change in the status quo (Uko 83). Wilkins in Ini Uko defines social consciousness as: “a sociological phenomenon most adequately expounded through the Marxist critical perception, which reveals social consciousness as manifest in individuals who are related organically by their social background” (*Gender & Identity...82*). Thus, social consciousness constitutes the driving force that motivates self-assertion, collective reaction and rebellion, empowerment and subsequent change. Predicated on this framework, Johnson’s and Salami’s plays explore gender assertiveness, sisterhood and revolution as a function of the female characters’ self and collective consciousness of the bourgeois oppression and the need for change.

Accordingly, in Johnson’s *Install*, with the emerging political developments in Ekondo, the women are now fully conscious of their subjugation and marginalisation by the men. They are now aware of the patriarchal instruments of oppression which include the biased traditional legal system, exclusion of women from the executive council and the manipulation of the male-cults. Hence, the women decide to come together and appoint a mother figure, Ufok iban (a mother/house of women) to represent them at the council, following the amendment the late king had effected in the law to pave way for women’s assertiveness and subsequent change in Ekondo land in due course. Inim Enem Uyo (the King’s praise singer/adviser) welcomes Ufok iban to the hallowed council: “Ufokiban, you are welcome... All women in their last meeting in the market square were unanimous that you were their *mother*, the very best representative they could have... The business of a successor to the throne of

Ekondo, concerns *all of us*” (58) (emphasis ours). Inim’s speech subtly raises the council’s consciousness of the need for gender equality and change in Ekondo politics.

Expectedly, on her entry into the council, the wise and articulate “new elder” named Ufok iban begins to assert the female voice, changing the dynamics of legislative debates to the women’s advantage. She moves a motion thus:

In that case, in keeping with the traditions of Ekondo, and in maintaining a continuum of sanctity in the royal throne of Ekondo, one of the king’s children with superlative ability is still remaining. The throne of Ekondo fits the Princess (61) (emphasis ours).

Her emphasis on the Princess’ credential – “superlative ability” – is significant. It serves to counter the androcentric stereotype of women as a folk lacking the “thinking skills for public life when compared with men” (Emenyi 38). Hence, she stresses her superb ability and intelligence which makes her more “fit” for the position of power, the “throne of Ekondo,” than the disabled and unfit son, Etiowo. Her motion as intended shocks the elderly men who kick against such a move, insisting that the throne is “exclusively for kings and not for queens” and that the late king had a “male-successor”. In reaction, Ufokiban vehemently argues that the male-successor “is not good enough” and that “the throne of Ekondo cannot be mounted by a disabled” as stipulated by tradition (63). Convinced, Nkakat admits:

There has to be a change. A slight change from the status quo. From what has always been. Because of the precarious circumstance of the season... (64).

That change, as posited by Ufokiban, is “the Princess ascending the throne of her father...” (64).

In the heat of the debate, we witness an act of sisterhood. On seeing the men bonding together in a hushed consultation, Ufokiban correspondingly reacts by dragging the Princess and they both meet with Edima, the docile wife of the late King, speaking in whispers. The next day, still at the prolonged debate, she challenges Edima to rise and assert herself instead of being passive in the

matter:

Witchcraft cannot destroy the daughter of the loudmouthed mother. Today, you will have to shout and scare away the manipulators of justice and reason. You cannot afford to resign to the passive role of a silent spectator. If it is profane for Etiowo to ascend the throne of Ekondo, then the gods are simply saying in clear terms, that, Princess should rule. You must rise up with me and shout this into existence (69) (emphasis ours).

Thus, Ufokiban raises the consciousness of Edima and opens her hitherto silent voice. She must “shout” her daughter into royalty.

Furthermore, rebellion ensues from the solidarity and assertiveness of Ufokiban, Edima and the entire village women and girls. The women revolt against the decision of the elderly men to consult the young men, but neglect the young women on the succession debate. With all their strength, the women scream “INSTALL THE PRINCESS, INSTALL THE PRINCES!” (77). To overcome the women, the cult leader invokes the masquerades which suddenly emerge with threatening, flaring machetes. The masquerades fail to heed Ukarakpa’s warning that “the palace of Ekondo opens to all. All the people here, including the women, have a duty to carry out...” (79). The men had forgotten that the women have a more dreaded and rebellious weapon of intimidation. To the masquerades, Ufokiban then marshals out the women’s threat:

Ufokiban: If you don’t leave now, I shall ask my women to strip themselves naked for you to see them very well... (Nne Mmatim lets her wrapper fall. She is only with her “Nkpin” ... The rattler quickly turns his head away. Ukarakpa, Ukpotio and Nkakat turn their heads away. The masquerades are overcome. Etiowo comes to them gently, and asks them to leave).

The fact remains if the masquerades should see in the women what they should not see, they will die a second time, never to resurrect again, according to the timely warning of Nkakat; hence, their retreat and disappearance. The village

girls seize the moment to chant the victorious song “Install The Princess” (79). The women storm out of the scene with threats to strip themselves naked in confrontation with the gods at the shrines and all the male cults from the groves. Ufokiban cries out:

Edima and Princess, in a time like this, the palace may not be the best place to be. The women are risking their lives in solidarity for change in Ekondo. Change in the right direction. And you are the anvil through which this change must spin. You cannot afford to rest in the palace. Come with me to the square. Let the hot sun of Ekondo bathe your naked royal skin for change; if we perish, we perish...” (83).

Edima and Princess join in the revolution. Here, we perceive the boldness, resilience and revolutionary spirit of the protesting women. Their disposition demonstrates Helen Chukwuma’s assertion that “It takes guts and courage to assert yourself in a society that subjugates you” (37). For some women, the fear of not belonging or of kicking against the status-quo keeps them quiet, caged in their bitterness.

The case is not different in Salami’s *Sweet*. As in *Install*, all the women are assertive, supportive and revolutionary. Initially, Aisosa, like Edima, was docile and very submissive to her husband. At his command, she resigns her medical appointment and becomes a kitchen material. However, she discovers her voice after eight years of silence with the return of the ungrateful Sota, her husband. Standing up, she tells Sota: “Mr Sota, if anyone has neglected the home it is you. You walked in majestically, and no one opposed you, now you want to make my life miserable. I am sorry I won’t take that from you...” (17). When Sota pours insults on her as someone “sweating like a Christmas goat,” and again asks her to come to bed, she tells him “Sorry, I am sleeping in the guest room. I’m sure you don’t want this fat, old flabby body beside you” (23). When asked to leave the house, she tearfully packs her children to Abuja to begin afresh. We see that Aisosa, like Princess or Ufokiban, is both a womanist and a motherist figure. In her conversation with Ede, she asserts her humanity, womanism and identity: “Am I a Zombie? No, I am human, with human feelings and desires yearning to be met too. I desire to be fulfilled as a woman”

(33). When approached by Sota for remarriage Aisosa rebels

I have no place for you in my heart. I have long programmed you out of my mind. As you can see, things are different now...Our lives together ended when you left for England...Sota, you can't put back the hand of the clock, no matter how hard you try (83-84).

This rebellion informs the title of the play *Sweet Revenge*.

Cheryl is very assertive and revolutionary from inception to the end. She indicts Sota and the country as being androcentric (11). She feels “the pain of the Nigerian women” and challenges Sota as a would-be senator to ensure that there is gender equality in Nigerian democracy and that “the labours of your heroines past shall not be in vain” (13). Cheryl finally walks out of marriage which she tags “fool’s paradise” (53) and reconciles herself with Aisota in solidarity to pay Sota back for fooling her over the years.

The village women, such as Madam Power-Power, Madam Show Dem, Madam Speaker and Madam Executive are very assertive, co-operative and rebellious. Together, they go to Senator Sota’s residence in Abuja and rebel against his pride and neglect of his constituency. Nosa had already warned him that “the combined force of women can deal with you thoroughly” (20). When Aboki, Sota’s gate-keeper, refuses them entrance, they pick stones and bang on the gate, forcing Sota out of his hiding. After much argument, Sota calls the police and the women are arrested and detained for three days. As a consequence, the women mobilise people and “sign a petition asking that Sota be recalled from the National Assembly” (63).

We equally notice with gladness the solidarity that emerges among the party women; Aisosa, Ede and Cheryl as well as that between Aisosa and her mother-in-law. The last sharply contrasts with the enmity that exists between Ramatuolaye and her Lady mother-in-law in Ba’s *So long a Letter*. Salami’s message is very explicit: for the fight for women’s emancipation to be won, the village women (educated and illiterate); the co-wives as well as the daughter-in-law and the mother-in-law must all come together and speak with one voice: “...dis time na women we want” (68), just like the women in *Install* shout: “Install the Princess”.

4.4 Gender Empowerment and Identity

Gender empowerment aims at transformation in socio-political conditions so as to address structural, systemic or institutionalized forms of subordination, oppression and exploitation. Carole Biewener and Marie- Helene Bacque observe that social problems are “rooted in structures that reproduce inequalities on a systematic basis” and “change can only come about through changes to these structures” (67). To them, becoming empowered necessarily entails the creation of new actors, formation of groups that have a “collective agency” and a “social or collective identity” (67).

Against this background, Johnson primarily aims at empowering the oppressed women of Ekondo through a change in the political structures. Through the King, he creates the needed avenue in the executive council through which the women can chart their way to the throne. “From now in Ekondo, one woman must be appointed to the elders’ forum...They too deserve better representations. They have a voice which must be heard” (36). With the appointment of Ufokiban to the elders’ forum soon after the king’s death, a new actor has been created in the political structure. Through her vociferous assertiveness and organisation of the women, the Princess is installed as the Queen of Ekondo. This is a clear demonstration of the female gender empowerment. It is hoped that with Princess on the throne, further changes will be effected to ensure gender equality as foreshadowed by Uko: “The world shall be different because you came... You would change the world... (92). The crowned Princess first kneels before Udobong, her school mate, and woos him: “Yes! Please take me as your wife!” This is a change in the tradition. It is usually a man that woos a woman in Ibibio culture. The Princess wooing Udobong reflects role reversal, an expression of gender empowerment. Next in her manifesto, the Queen pledges to be “the best *wife* and *mother* there would ever be” (emphasis ours). With a mother on the throne, the female gender has assumed a positive identity in Ekondo.

In *Sweet*, Salami empowers the women and redeems their identity. Aisosa is not only educated, but also a consultant gynaecologist. She works in the National Medical Research Centre after her eviction. Hence, she is able to cope with single motherhood. She now desires “to be fulfilled as a woman” (33) and puts her past behind. The fulfilment comes when the women elect her to the position of a Senator. She is further empowered to the office of the Senate

President; an office she occupies for two terms. This gender empowerment and identity appears to be a fulfilment of Flora Nwapa's vision who believes that the "African woman writer is urged to break new ground by projecting the future of a female president" ("Women and Creative Writing in Africa" 531). Besides, Cheryl leads a coalition of groups and international organizations to award Aisosa with \$300,000 for leading an exemplary life in the face of adversity (60). With such remarkable achievements, the hitherto negative image and identity of the female gender has worn a new look.

4.4 Discussion

From the foregoing analysis, it is discovered that both plays have explored similar gender motifs in their unique settings and background. First is their focus on gender subjugation and abuse. The female gender is oppressed and abused through the machinery of patriarchy. The male gender makes the laws to position themselves permanently in power, while the female gender suffers in silence.

Again, both plays frown at gender disparity in political representation. In *Install*, the male gender manipulates the traditional legal system and the male cults to dislodge the female gender from governance. Thus, the village setting and background makes this manipulation possible. Whereas in *Sweet*, the cosmopolitan setting and background has excluded the use of traditional instruments of intimidation such as the male cults and female nakedness.

Besides, both plays emphasise the need for change in the socio-political structures through the female gender assertiveness, sisterhood and revolution. At this level, educated women should be utilized to organise the women, who themselves must come together despite their differences to fight for their empowerment.

Again, the plays stress more on the female gender empowerment and identity. This can only be achieved through changes in the status-quo. Both plays tend to emphasise that without empowerment of the female gender to positions of power, there would be no gender equality in societies.

It is discovered that the playwrights have shared similar vision which is to empower Nigerian (African) women and mothers who have suffered neglect,

subjugation, marginalisation and oppression in marriage, politics, religion; indeed, both private and public spheres of human existence. Empowerment entails changing the dynamics and operations of patriarchy and traditionalism to accommodate the female gender in governance and establish gender equality and complementarity. In line with their vision, African women and mothers, including girls, cannot remain passive, docile, weak, divided and uneducated and hope to climb any influential positions of power in contemporary societies. Instead, they need to bond and assert themselves individually and collectively. Besides, they should take active part in the local, national and international politics through which they could reposition themselves and redeem their bastardised image. This is in line with O.F. Siwoku-Awi's submission in his investigation of gender motifs in the works of Calixthe Bayala and Ama Ata Aidoo, that African feminist concerns are meant to raise female consciousness, subvert patrocetric culture, which lauds male hegemony and to reconstruct female gender by making the woman valuable and indispensable to an emergent economy in budding African societies.

Accordingly, Effiong Johnson in *Install* dramatises the subjugation and marginalisation of the rural women, mothers and girls of Ekondo, a fictionalised village in Ibibio land in the face challenging political conflicts. The women's exclusion from the elders' forum promotes patriarchal dominance and unfair repression of the female gender, thereby deepening the political crises. Consequently, the appointment of Ufokiban into the elders' forum ushers in a female voice in the council, culminating in the unprecedented installation of a woman, Princess, as a mother on the throne, a symbol of positive change, fairness, equality, freedom, fruitfulness and development.

On her part, Irene Salami exposes, in *Sweet*, the evil of dehumanisation of the female gender in contemporary Nigerian society. The play depicts a bizarre account of a man's insensitivity and subjugation of women. Sota Ojo marries Aisosa, a consultant gynaecologist, but stops her from practicing her profession in order to take care of his needs and those of their four children. Aisosa consequently suffers abandonment, abuse, betrayal and divorce from her husband. However, Aisosa, whose name means "no one is greater than God," eventually survives her ordeals and revenges her wicked husband, by replacing him as twice a Senator in Nigeria's National Assembly. Her empowerment, like in Johnson's *Install*, is propelled by the bonding, assertiveness and daring revolution of the oppressed women.

4 Conclusion

In response to Nigerians' yearning for the desired change and restructuring in the nation's socio-political system, Effiong Johnson's and Irene Salami's *Install* and *Sweet* respectively dramatise the changing patterns of women's participation in politics. Augusto Boal's *Poetics of the Oppressed* cited in Agatha Njideka Nwanya and Chris Ojemudia, posits that "Theatre is a weapon; only the oppressed can wield it" ("Gender and Creativity: The Contributions of Nigerian Female Writers" 55). The plays represent a reflection on a positive shift which is gradually empowering the oppressed women on key political positions in Nigeria. Anchoring on the total theatre aesthetics and dramatic techniques of future projection and flashback, the plays effectively capture the prevailing mood and sensitivity of the time as regards gender equality, complementarity and empowerment through equitable distribution of power, wealth and opportunities between the genders.

The battle by Nigerian female and male writers to write women into positive relevance, beginning with Flora Nwapa's *Efuru* through Tess Onwueme's *Reign of Wazobia* and to Johnson's *Install* and Salami's *Sweet* unarguably assumes radical-cum-accommodating stance with the entrance of the Princess and Aisosa into politics. From total passivity to aggressive politicking, Nigerian women and mothers are gradually emerging from their shadows. In reality more women have entered mainstream politics, although the number is still negligible when compared to their active male counterpart. The vision of the playwrights in making the female gender to displace the male in top positions in governance is both realistic and futuristic. In 2003 Anambra State House of Assembly Elections, a female candidate, Njideka Ezeigwe, displaced her male opponent through the court and was able to clinch the party ticket and position till the end of the first term tenure. She even emerged for the second time in another party in the most controversial 2007 Elections. April 2011 and May 2015 elections represent a dynamic shift in the pattern of Nigerian politics as more women got elected position in both state and federal Houses of Assembly. It is equally futuristic since Nigeria is yet to have a female Senate President or even the nation's President as Helen Sheriff-Johnson of Liberia.

In advocating for women's empowerment and gender complementarity in private and public spheres, the playwrights challenge the misogynist and the generality of the populace to the fact that dehumanisation or marginalisation of

the woman being is an evil that endangers good human relations and progress in society. Johnson interrogates the male folk “Can a man afford to joke with a woman’s interest and hope to return home to peace?” (99) The answer is an affirmative “No”. Therefore, the girl-child is as important as the boy-child; hence roles must be responsibly shared. Salami’s *Sweet Revenge* as a title is a metaphorical satire for gender intrigues and squabbles that characterise most family affairs. In the play, it is sweet revenge for Aisosa to reject Sota when he comes back on his knees for remarriage and for her as she dislodges him from the Senatorial seat. Salami further advocates for female education and contributions to society as requirements for empowerment. Her women are powerful and educated. She posits that “Our foremothers were known to have accomplished great things; displayed exceptional skill and talent, stood up against oppression, injustice and contributed much to the society” (99). Hence, Aisosa is a consultant gynaecologist and later a Senator. Madam Power Power is a political activist. Cheryl is an international model. The case is the same with Johnson’s Ufokiban, Princess and Nne Mmatim. These are a new breed of empowered women and mothers: brave, active, determined, pushful, articulate and intelligent. However, there still exist some patriarchal roadblocks which cripple and frustrate the smooth ride and chances of modern women and mothers to positions of authority. Therefore, to empower the female gender and effect possible gender equality, there must be a positive change in the existing socio-political structures of patriarchy in order to usher in an articulate and intelligent female voice, through whom a collective consciousness, sisterhood and organised revolution could be achieved among the female folk. Through such bonding, more changes could be effected in the status-quo, leading to an expansion of the phenomenal female space in both traditional and cosmopolitan societies.

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